

HOW TO PREVENT WORKPLACE ACCIDENTS AND SAVE WORKERS' LIVES? TACKLING THE INVISIBLE TRIO OF DEPRESSION, ANXIETY AND INSOMNIA BEFORE IT'S TOO LATE

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Abstract: *Occupational safety and health is a discipline with global ramifications - workplace accidents and related diseases cause almost 2.78 million deaths each year and significant economic losses. Mental health conditions (specifically depression, anxiety and insomnia) are closely linked to increased workplace accident risk and impaired job performance. The aim of this paper is to conduct a literature review examining past research on the bidirectional relationships between these mental health disorders and occupational accidents. Depression and anxiety not only elevate accident risk but can also result from traumatic workplace incidents. Insomnia is similarly associated with higher accident rates, particularly in high-risk professions such as transportation. Prevention strategies highlighted include workplace health promotion programs, cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT), early symptom detection, and coping techniques. Despite promising findings, the literature is limited by cross-sectional designs, self-reported data, and some confounding variables which have not been accounted for. Practical implications encompass integrating mental health into occupational safety training, risk assessment, and nurturing cooperation between healthcare professionals and employers. Potential future directions involve longitudinal studies and studying the combined effect of multiple mental health disorders. Ultimately, addressing mental health in occupational settings is essential for enhancing worker well-being, organizational success and societal progress.*

Keywords: Workplace Accidents, Depression, Insomnia, Anxiety, Mental Health

1. INTRODUCTION

The subject of occupational safety and health is a highly relevant and multidimensional issue that affects workers, companies and legislators alike [1]. Indeed, it is estimated that annually 2.78 million workers worldwide die from workplace accidents and work-related diseases, whilst an additional 374 million workers face the consequences of non-lethal workplace accidents. This implies that on an annual basis nearly 2 million people are dying because of work-related causes. Workplace-related fatalities surpass the average yearly deaths from traffic accidents (999,000), war (502,000), violence (563,000) and HIV/AIDS (312,000) [2].

Aside from the immense human cost and suffering, this global phenomenon also takes on an economic toll: approximately 4 % of the global Gross Domestic Product is impacted each year [3]. To illustrate this concerning statistic with an example (a plethora of other workplace hazards exists), the International Labour Organization provides an estimate that there is potential for \$361 billion to be saved on a global level via enforcing enhanced occupational safety and health procedures with the aim of preventing injuries from heat hazards [4]. Overall, the burden borne by society (ie. Families, businesses and governments) includes compensation payments, decreased company competitiveness on the market, early retirements, absenteeism, higher unemployment rate and impoverished households [5].

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In order to adequately approach and mitigate all of these risk factors, it is imperative to understand that the field of occupational safety and health is tightly interwoven with a multitude of other areas, including psychology. In that respect, depression, anxiety and insomnia are both amongst the most commonly diagnosed mental health issues worldwide and are inextricably linked to occupational injuries and critical work incidents. In fact, findings from a number of past studies confirm that there is a connection between the occurrence of workplace accidents and the previously mentioned mental health problems [6,7].

In light of that, the aim of this paper is to conduct a literature review of previous research done on the topic of workers' depression, anxiety and insomnia in the context of occupational accidents. Appropriate prevention strategies will also be described. In addition, gaps and limitations in the literature will be discussed, as well as the implications for a future direction in research and for society in general.

In order to find relevant sources, a literature review utilizing PubMed, Scopus and Google Scholar was done. The search terms/key words included "workplace accidents", "depression", "anxiety", "insomnia" and "mental health". Peer-reviewed journal articles were mainly prioritized, with a focus on adult employees in occupational/industrial contexts. Papers that examined clinical populations or non-work-related injuries were excluded.

2. MENTAL HEALTH AND WORKPLACE ACCIDENTS

2.1 Depression at the workplace

Depression hampers work performance and productivity, with workers reporting that their work injuries and/or accidents are a product of this condition [6]. This is also in conjunction with other factors. For instance, one 12-month study done on a sample of manufacturing workers has shown depression represents a risk factor for absenteeism at work due to disease or accidents [8]. Another paper states how one of the negative aspects of depression is that it leads to an increased incidence of occupational accidents [9]. Notably, one study from China found that depression is negatively associated with safety participation in an industrial setting, which may mediate accident risk [10].

The relationship goes both ways. Results from one paper demonstrate that workplace accidents leave a dire effect on the mental health of victims; namely, in the form of both posttraumatic and depressive symptoms [11]. A study about male municipal firefighters found that there was a 7.4 times higher risk of being categorized as depressed for firefighters who survived injuries and accidents in the 2-year time period of testing compared to those who have not lived through such an experience [12].

Most of the above-mentioned articles suggest programs to either promote mental health or take concrete measures to reduce depressive symptoms at work [10,11,12]. One literature review highlights a multifaceted idea for depression prevention in the workplace, including working on personal resilience, screening workers who perform high-risk jobs and taking adequate measures to lower the risk, education and training within the company, as well as blending occupational and healthcare systems to ensure smooth access to timely high-quality interventions [13]. More specifically, one meta-analysis states that, based on evidence, CBT-based programs (Cognitive Behavioural Therapy) are more effective than other interventions and highlights that evidence-based interventions should be the cornerstone of helping workers suffering from depression [14].

2.2 Anxiety at the workplace

Anxiety and the occurrence of workplace accidents are tightly related [6]. Indeed, one study focusing on the oil and gas extraction industries elaborates how a greater sense of anxiety in offshore workers

may lead to an impaired job performance, decreased productivity, and increased vulnerability to occupational accidents [15]. Regarding the safety aspect, this notion has been tested by researchers in China who administered a survey on 383 elevator workers, measuring amongst other traits, how anxious they are. Trait anxiety in this case refers to the inclination to experience fear or worry in the form of a consistent personality characteristic. It was concluded that anxiety could be a predictor of workplace injuries, implying that recruiters should strive to select the elevator installers and repairers that are more assured of themselves, and display a higher degree of self-confidence [16]. Similarly, another paper found a statistically significant correlation between the rate of workplace accidents and professional risks in the pre-hospital setting – a list which was provided by a representative sample of Mobile Emergency Service workers [17].

The relationship between anxiety and work accidents is a bidirectional one. An accident is a traumatic event at its core, and as such, there is a high risk of developing both Posttraumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) and comorbid psychological disorders. A study done on a sample of 297 policemen who responded to a self-report questionnaire found that policemen who were exposed to any kind of accident either as victims or witnesses were far more likely to report feeling anxious as compared to their colleagues who experienced none [18].

When it comes to anxiety prevention and professional risk mitigation strategies, one article highlights the significance of detecting anxiety symptoms early on (particularly when it manifests itself via prolonged absences from work) and taking appropriate action in time by implementing clinical interventions. Clinicians should have a sense of urgency as soon as the first symptoms become evident, in order to be able to provide the effective treatment [19]. According to a Malaysian study designed as a mixed-model intervention on manufacturing workers, workplace health promotion program (WHP) shows promising results in reducing work-related anxiety, improving coping abilities, raising quality of life and enhancing the overall mental health status of an individual [20].

2.3 Insomnia at the workplace

Insomnia represents the most common sleeping disorder and has been identified as a significant public health problem, linked with a high burden for the community, including work accidents (via sleep deprivation), daytime functioning at the workplace and health-related quality of life [21]. According to one study done on a sample of 953 workers from Québec, Canada, 25% of individuals with insomnia had been absent from work relative to 17.1% of good sleepers. Non-motor-vehicle accidents also took place at higher rates in the group which reported having insomnia syndrome (12.5 % as compared to 6.4 % for good sleepers) [22]. This study, however, does not cover specific high-risk professional categories, as does another one which successfully finds a link between insomnia and road accidents on a sample of 949 truck drivers. After implementing a research design involving a cross-sectional survey (and correcting for the factors of obstructive sleep apnea, excessive daytime sleepiness, short sleep duration etc.) the study in question found that truck drivers suffering from insomnia had a nearly two times greater risk of experiencing driving accidents. Even more strikingly, it found that they had a more than three times greater risk of experiencing near-miss accidents, in contrast to their non-insomniac counterparts [23]. Similarly, one more study, after having its sample undergo an interview with a clinical physician and respond to a self-administered questionnaire on work-related criteria, found that insomniac workers also had an increased accident rate while driving and, alarmingly, a three times higher risk of having 2-3 serious road accidents [24].

Taking past research into account, one review summarizes and synthesizes them to reach the following conclusion: symptoms of insomnia elevate accident risk in the work environment [25]. Targeted, goal-specific insomnia interventions may provide the backdrop for enhancing sleep quality and work productivity, based on cross-sectional and pre-post intervention analyses from a big multinational manufacturing company [26]. A randomized controlled intervention with a waiting list

control group demonstrated that Group CBT for alleviating insomnia symptoms given to workers did not resolve sleep issues if considering the group collectively, while it was shown that the intervention decreased insomnia in workers with regular daytime duties [27]. It has also been suggested that the priority of supervisor safety can derive circumstantial strength that may stop employees from unsafe actions despite displaying insomnia symptoms [28]. Furthermore, certain significant preventive coping strategies for tiredness connected with shift work (ie. napping and being exposed to bright daylight) have already been researched and are generally seen as effective [29]. When it comes to other solutions, effectiveness trials are required to establish whether increased screening, outreach, and treatment of employees with insomnia would yield a positive return on investment for companies [30].

3. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

One of the key findings from previous literature is that the three mental health issues outlined above – depression, anxiety and insomnia - are associated with a higher rate of workplace accidents. [6,7]. In the case of anxiety and/or depression, this relationship goes both ways [11,12,18]. Prevention strategies include workplace health promotion programs, interventions (eg. CBT) and common coping techniques [14,20,29]. Theoretically speaking, this is in line with the integrated approach model proposed in a recent *Debate* piece written by a group of Australian scientists, which would address the needs and concerns of all societal stakeholders on all levels of the social hierarchy (Figure 1) [31].

Figure 1 The three threads of the integrated approach to workplace mental health.

Source: LaMontagne, A.D., Martin, A., Page, K.M. et al. Workplace mental health: developing an integrated intervention approach. *BMC Psychiatry* 14, 131 (2014).

Gaps and limitations in the literature include too many cross-sectional study designs used, instead of longitudinal ones (ones taking place over a longer period of time). Additionally, the information from the questionnaires in past research were self-reported, and hence may lead to recall bias, a prevalent

occurrence in studies utilizing population survey data. Finally, there was a lack of data on several possible confounding variables, ie. family history of mental disorders, other traumatic life events outside of the workplace, and psychosocial climate in the work environment.

Practical implications encompass both state and company policies. Mental health problems should be a key component of occupational health and safety training within the organisation. Moreover, organisations should carry out professional risk assessment targeting mental health. Deeper communication and cooperation are required between health care professionals (ie. doctors, nurses etc.) and employers.

Future directions could involve expanding research to involve all social actors, both organisational and non-organisational – testing both for depressive, anxiety and insomnia symptoms and monitoring how the two settings differ in terms of accident rate. Testing for other common mental health disorders too – such as PTSD – and researching the mutual interplay of all of these mental health issues on large, stratified samples of international workers (the goal being formulating a kind of global intervention in the workplace) would bring both higher statistical power and higher validity of results. Then, applying both workplace health promotion programs and interventions, as well as measuring how they relate to company economics (whether they aid in reducing medical expenses and other costs for employers) would provide stronger justification for their implementation, if the results turn out to be positive. In conclusion, nothing in the world of occupational health and safety is an isolated concept and/or actor. The well-being of the worker, success of the organisation, work productivity and the betterment of society are only parts of one complex structure ensuring global progress – both technologically and economically.

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